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Unlocking Smart City Development: Exploring the Impact of Urbanization, Technological Innovation, and Foreign Investment in Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the significance of urbanization, industrialization, technological innovation, foreign direct investment (FDI), and economic growth for the development of smart cities in Pakistan. Data from the World Development Indicators (WDI) spanning the period of 1975 to 2020 was utilized. Various econometric techniques were employed, including Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analysis to investigate the relationships between dependent and independent variables. Outliers were detected to assess the degree of deviation from the regression line, and Robust Least Squares techniques were applied to address their impact on the dataset. The findings indicate that technology innovation and urbanization have a positive impact on the development of smart cities in Pakistan. However, other factors such as industrialization, FDI, and economic growth may also play significant roles, although their impact was not as pronounced in this study. The study emphasizes the importance of implementing proper policies and encouraging government and private sector investment to facilitate smart cities development in Pakistan. It underscores the need for strategic planning and collaboration between various stakeholders to realize the full potential of smart city initiatives in the country.

Keywords: Smart Cities Development; Urbanization; Industrialization; Economic Growth; Technology innovation; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

The global shift towards smartness, encompassing materials, cities, management, and sustainability, has popularized the concept of "smart cities." In essence, a smart city, also referred to as a digital or informed city, utilizes information and communication technology to perceive, analyze, and integrate crucial data from municipal administration systems. However, what defines a smart city in the local Pakistani context? Urbanization, while fostering economic prosperity, also intensifies resource consumption and energy demand, potentially compromising ecological environments (Yu, 2021). As populations migrate from rural to urban settings, significant societal, health, educational, and economic impacts emerge, alongside job creation and improved access to essential services like healthcare (Ventriglio 2021). The burgeoning demand for urbanization is palpable, with a notable shift towards city living, signaling modernization and economic growth. Yet, rapid urban growth poses challenges, including land use conflicts and potential threats to food security (Wang 2021).

Industrialization has historically elevated living standards, initially catalyzed by the British Industrial Revolution, albeit with varying impacts across nations (Nouhoum Touré 2021). Factors such as resource reallocation, skilled labor migration, and educational disparities contribute to the complex landscape of economic development (Kan & Chen 2022). For many countries, industrialization remains a cornerstone of social and economic progress, aligning with the Sustainable Development Goals to alleviate poverty and foster inclusive growth (Amoah & Jehu-Appiah 2022). The transition towards smart cities necessitates embracing technological advancements to effectively manage urban centers and cater to burgeoning populations. As cities evolve, so do the challenges, prompting governments and technology firms to collaborate on innovative solutions for improved governance and service delivery (Troisi et al 2021). Smart cities aim for sustainability and efficiency, addressing pressing global issues such as environmental degradation, energy consumption, and urbanization challenges (Kim et al 2021). In Pakistan, as urbanization accelerates, the adoption of contemporary technology becomes imperative for effective city management and enhanced citizen services. The transformation of conventional cities into smart urban hubs is gaining traction globally, driven by diverse local needs and resource availability. Each city's journey towards smartness is unique, shaped by its distinct challenges, societal dynamics, and aspirations. Collaboration between city authorities and technology providers is paramount to establish the requisite infrastructure for improved governance and service delivery across various sectors, including civil defense, law enforcement, utilities, and transportation engineering.

Smart cities offer a multitude of benefits, leveraging data-driven insights to efficiently manage assets, resources, and services, thereby enhancing overall operations. With urbanization emerging as a predominant global trend in the twenty-first century, the significance of smart cities becomes increasingly apparent. By 2050, an estimated 70% of the world's population, representing 2.5 billion additional individuals, will reside in urban areas, with Africa and Asia experiencing the bulk of this urbanization surge. Countries like India, Pakistan, Indonesia, and Nigeria are expected to witness significant urban population growth, fostering both megacities and smaller urban settlements (Gondal 2021). The concept of smart cities revolves around four key pillars: Social Infrastructure, Physical Infrastructure, Institutional Infrastructure (including Governance), and Economic Infrastructure. These pillars serve as the foundation for promoting economic growth and enhancing residents' quality of life while preserving the city's cultural heritage and ecological balance. The primary objectives of smart city initiatives include improving citizens' quality of life, meeting their needs, and fostering local area development in a sustainable manner (Gondal 2021).

In the context of Pakistan, our study aims to achieve several objectives:

1. Assessing the role and impact of Economic growth on smart cities development: Fluctuations in GDP can influence the overall development trajectory of smart cities, with economic growth trends affecting various aspects of urban development.
2. Exploring the role of technology innovation and technology export in smart cities development: Technological advancements and the export of technology can significantly contribute to the advancement of smart city infrastructure and services.
3. Analyzing the implications of rural to urban migration on smart cities development: The migration of people from rural to urban areas presents challenges and opportunities for smart city development, which warrant thorough examination.
4. Investigating the role of foreign direct investment (FDI) in Economic growth and smart cities development: FDI plays a pivotal role in driving economic growth and fostering infrastructure development, including initiatives related to smart cities.
5. Examining the impact of industrialization on smart cities development: Industrialization can have both positive and negative effects on smart city development, influencing factors such as resource utilization, environmental sustainability, and economic prosperity.

Through these objectives, our study aims to provide valuable insights into the dynamics of smart cities development in Pakistan, shedding light on key factors shaping urbanization trends and strategies for sustainable growth.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following literature review presented a dynamic overview of the study's research work, i.e., Zhang et al. (2021) observed that air quality stands out as one of the most readily perceived environmental factors, with air pollution posing a significant challenge in many low- and middle-income countries, especially in urban settings. Their review explored the historical trends of air pollution across various stages of urbanization in high-, middle-, and low-income countries, offering insights into the evolving relationship between urbanization and air pollution. Meanwhile, Danish et al. (2020) examined the interplay between real income, renewable energy, urbanization, rents from natural resources, and the ecological footprint of the BRICS economy, suggesting policy implications for sustainable development. Ahmad et al. (2021) empirically investigated the role of industrialization and urbanization in achieving carbon neutrality in Pakistan, considering foreign direct investment and economic growth as control variables. However, their findings did not indicate support for carbon neutrality based on the examined variables. Rahman et al. (2021) analyzed the relationship between CO₂ emissions and industrialization, energy imports, carbon intensity, economic progress, and gross capital formation in Pakistan from 1971 to 2019, advocating for measures to reduce carbon emissions for improved economic progress. Myeong & Shahzad (2021) proposed a technologically driven air quality solution for smart cities, emphasizing the potential economic and social benefits through data-driven smart city development. Farooq et al. (2021) investigated the existence of the environmental Kuznets curve (EKC) in Pakistan and found a U-shaped association between economic growth and environmental quality, confirming the presence of the EKC phenomenon. Zhang et al. (2022) explored factors influencing electricity consumption, such as energy costs, economic growth, industrialization, and urbanization, providing insights for policymakers in addressing challenges related to fossil fuel reliance amid economic expansion and urbanization in Pakistan. Khan & Zia (2021) introduced the concept of smart cities and discussed key components, security aspects, and potential benefits.

Azam et al. (2022) investigated the causal nexus between urbanization, industrialization, energy use, national income,

international trade, and CO₂ emissions in OPEC member countries, advocating for environmentally friendly policies. Lam et al. (2021) proposed an innovative approach to sustainable urban planning through Transit-Oriented Development (TOD) and Information and Communication Technology (ICT), aiming to bridge socioeconomic-environmental gaps in developing countries. Goa and Yaun (2022) examined the implications of satellite monitoring and smart city initiatives on air pollution governance, highlighting the abatement impact in large smart cities and resource-based urban areas. Abbasi et al. (2022) assessed the impact of economic globalization, financial development, energy use, and technological innovation on consumption and emissions in Pakistan, emphasizing the need for renewable energy promotion to achieve sustainable development goals. Islam (2021) explored the impact of globalization, foreign direct investment, economic growth, trade, innovation, urbanization, and energy consumption on CO₂ emissions in Bangladesh, suggesting policy directions for environmental quality improvement. Munir & Ameer (2021) analyzed the nonlinear relationships between urbanization, trade liberalization, economic growth, technology, and environmental pollution in African and Asian emerging economies, highlighting the importance of environmental regulations and green growth strategies. Khurshid et al. (2021) examined the role of eco-patents and trademarks in reducing carbon emissions, emphasizing the impact of energy consumption, urbanization, and economic expansion. Abid et al. (2021) investigated the impact of technical innovation, financial development, foreign direct investment, energy use, and urbanization on carbon emissions in G8 member countries, highlighting the need for better regulations and emission reduction strategies. Zhang & Chen (2021) utilized the stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) model to analyze carbon emission efficiency and its determinants in China's Yangtze River Economic Belt, suggesting measures to improve efficiency through economic restructuring and green technology development. Chenghu et al. (2021) studied the relationship between tourism development, technological innovation, urbanization, and environmental deterioration in Chinese provinces, emphasizing the need for balanced policies to mitigate environmental impacts.

Dong et al. (2021) examined the urbanization-environment nexus in Sub-Saharan African nations, advocating for collaborative efforts to support urbanization while ensuring environmental sustainability. Haldar & Sharma (2021) investigated the effects of urbanization on per capita energy consumption and emissions in India, highlighting the importance of reducing energy intensity to mitigate carbon emissions. Mohsin et al. (2022) explored the relationship between economic development, energy use, foreign direct investment, agriculture, industrialization, and urban population increase in Pakistan, emphasizing the role of green technology and fiscal policies. Chen et al. (2021) analyzed the relationships between human capital, urbanization, and ecological footprint across economies, emphasizing the need for environmental management strategies amid urbanization. Bosah et al. (2021) experimentally explored the impact of energy consumption, economic growth, and urbanization on carbon emissions, underscoring the importance of energy-efficient urban planning and emission reduction strategies. Lin et al. (2021) investigated the influence of new-type urbanization on energy saving in Chinese cities, highlighting its potential for resource efficiency. Kiani et al. (2022) discussed the impact of technological advancements on environmental degradation in South and Southeast Asian countries, advocating for energy efficiency initiatives and trade-related environmental regulations. Fan et al. (2021) evaluated the economic, social, ecological, and resource transformations resulting from city development plans in resource-based cities in China. Jermstittiparsert (2021) examined the role of industrialization, urbanization, income inequality, and human capital in environmental sustainability, particularly in ASEAN economies. Jabeen et al. (2022) estimated the energy potential of combustible fractions in domestic solid waste in Faisalabad, Pakistan, highlighting the potential for energy generation from waste. Wenlong et al. (2022) assessed the impact of energy efficiency, technological advancements, trade openness, and institutional quality on environmental quality in Asian economies, emphasizing the need for sustainable development policies. Nathaniel et al. (2021) explored the relationship between natural resources, globalization, urbanization, and environmental deterioration in Latin American countries, advocating for human capital development and sustainability practices in the natural resource sector. The literature review emphasized the need to explore the importance of smart cities development in the context of Pakistan.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This section outlines the data sources and various econometric techniques employed in the analysis. The dependent variable under investigation is Smart Cities Development (SCD), while the independent variables include urbanization, industrialization, technological innovation, foreign direct investment, and economic growth. To compute the SCD variable, which comprises electronic consumption, water resource, and clean environment, data for the remaining variables are sourced from World Development Indicators (WDI). However, it's noted that data specifically for SCD is not available in the WDI dataset. Therefore, SCD can be computed using the following formula:

$$SCD = \frac{Electricity\ Consumption + Water\ Resources + CO_2\ emissions}{3}$$

Table 1 shows the list of variables for ready reference.

Table 1: List of Variables

Variables	Symbol	Unit
Smart Cities Development	SCD	Index
Urbanization	URB	Million

Variables	Symbol	Unit
Industrialization	IND	Annual growth %
Technology innovation	TECH EXP	US Dollar
Foreign direct investment	FDI	Net inflow growth %
Economic Growth	GDP	% growth rate

Source: World Bank (2023).

The econometric techniques to be employed include ordinary least squares (OLS), robust least squares (RLS), outlier detection, descriptive statistics, and Granger causality tests. The regression model for our variables is as follows:

$$SCD = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (URB) + \beta_2 (IND) + \beta_3 (GDP \text{ pc}) + \beta_4 (FDI) + \beta_5 (TECH \text{ exp}) + \mu \quad (1)$$

When dealing with large errors or influential observations in the model, the robust least squares method is employed as a proxy for the ordinary least squares (OLS) method.

1. M-estimation, introduced by Huber in 1973, aims to reduce large errors and detect outliers in dependent variables.
2. S-estimation, developed by Rousseeuw and Yohai in 1984, is a computationally intensive method used to detect outliers in independent variables.
3. MM-estimation, presented by Yohai in 1987, is utilized to identify outliers in both dependent and independent variables.

The Granger causality approach examines the causal relationships between variables. It involves a statistical hypothesis test to determine whether one variable can be used to forecast another.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The descriptive statistics provided in Table 2 offer a comprehensive overview of the dataset. The Smart Cities Development (SCD), serving as the dependent variable, exhibits a mean value of 80017.61, with a maximum of 143908.6 and a minimum of 50429.73. Among the independent variables—Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Industrialization (IND), Technological Innovation (TECH.EXP), and Urbanization (URB)—the mean GDP is 4.733, ranging from 10.215 to 4.839, while FDI shows a mean of 0.818, with values varying between 3.668 and 0.615. Industrialization demonstrates a mean of 5.225, with values ranging from 17.374 to 4.929, whereas Technological Innovation exhibits a mean of 2.770, with a range of 3.960 to 2.640. Urbanization, with a mean of 45680120, spans from 82094635 to 43166563. Skewness analysis indicates that SCD is positively skewed (0.72), suggesting a distribution skewed towards the right, while GDP displays negative skewness (-0.102), indicating a distribution skewed towards the left. Additionally, the Kurtosis values highlight the peakedness of the frequency distribution, with SCD exhibiting positive Kurtosis (2.22) and Urbanization showing negative Kurtosis (1.868), suggesting variations in the distribution shapes of the variables.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

	SMART_CIT...	GDP	FDI	IND	TECH_EXP	URB
Mean	80017.61	4.733647	0.818940	5.225145	2.77E+08	45280120
Median	70607.53	4.839699	0.615677	4.929588	2.64E+08	43166563
Maximum	143908.6	10.21570	3.668323	17.37416	3.96E+08	82094635
Minimum	50429.73	-0.935390	0.062428	-5.206873	2.33E+08	17600233
Std. Dev.	30455.54	2.187787	0.772676	3.891204	33603294	19315656
Skewness	0.725573	-0.102368	2.296042	-0.033765	2.172060	0.285321
Kurtosis	2.224739	3.162689	8.214433	4.731043	6.841384	1.868053
Jarque-Bera	5.188142	0.131070	92.53195	5.752049	64.45291	3.079962
Probability	0.074715	0.936566	0.000000	0.056358	0.000000	0.214385
Sum	3680810.	217.7478	37.67122	240.3567	1.28E+10	2.08E+09
Sum Sq. Dev.	4.17E+10	215.3885	26.86629	681.3662	5.08E+16	1.68E+16
Observations	46	46	46	46	46	46

Source: World Bank (2023).

Figure 1 illustrates the presence of outliers within the dataset. Outliers are data points that significantly deviate from the rest of the data, making them stand out as unusual or exceptional values. These outliers can skew statistical analyses and distort interpretations of the data, potentially leading to inaccurate conclusions. Identifying and addressing outliers is crucial for ensuring the reliability and validity of statistical analyses and model predictions.

Figure 1: Outliers Detection
Source: Author’s work.

As depicted in the scatterplot, the majority of our independent variables cluster closely around the regression line, indicating a reasonable fit to the model. However, it’s noteworthy that the technology export variable, represented by the red data points, exhibits some values that deviate notably from the regression line. These outliers can potentially introduce bias and affect the accuracy of our model predictions. To address this issue and enhance the robustness of our analysis, applying robust least squares regression, such as the Rubout least square method, could effectively mitigate the impact of outliers on our model’s performance. The outcomes from the robust least squares regression analysis (see, Table 3) reveal that urbanization and technology exports emerge as the predominant factors influencing smart cities development in Pakistan. These findings underscore the significant impact of urbanization and technological innovation on the advancement and progression of smart city initiatives within the country. By identifying these key determinants, policymakers and stakeholders can better focus their efforts and resources on fostering urbanization strategies and promoting technological advancements to further propel the development of smart cities across Pakistan. To sustain rapid economic growth, it’s imperative for the nation to attract foreign capital and ensure a high quality of living for its residents. Accelerating investments in sustainable smart cities becomes crucial in this pursuit (Pan et al., 2023). Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) can play a pivotal role in fostering low-carbon innovation, and the development of smart cities can amplify FDI’s positive spillover effects on such innovations (Ye et al., 2021). Additionally, Gross Domestic Product (GDP) stands as a fundamental factor for the sustained long-term expansion and development of cities (Musa, 2017). By addressing urban challenges, cities can promote economic development. Strategies such as waste management, including techniques like reuse and recycling to mitigate the impact of waste generation resulting from industrialization and population growth, are vital in this endeavor (do Livramento Gonçalves et al., 2021). Furthermore, the Fourth Industrial Revolution is poised to influence various variables closely tied to the ability of cities to achieve sustainability.

Table 3: Robust Least Squares Regression Estimates

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
FDI	1114.549	1592.033	0.700079	0.4839
GDP	822.9626	664.9066	1.237712	0.2158
IND	-328.5183	370.4507	-0.886807	0.3752
TECH_EXP	0.000125	4.26E-05	2.927135	0.0034
URB	0.001407	8.68E-05	16.21411	0.0000
C	-21464.20	10444.77	-2.055019	0.0399

Robust Statistics			
R-squared	0.819399	Adjusted R-squared	0.796824
Rw-squared	0.966058	Adjust Rw-squared	0.966058
Akaike info criterion	40.14355	Schwarz criterion	54.73635
Deviance	1.41E+09	Scale	6660.432
Rn-squared statistic	911.3868	Prob(Rn-squared stat.)	0.000000

5. CONCLUSIONS

The concept of Smart Cities Development (SCD) has gained significant traction globally, reflecting a collective effort among nations to cultivate safer, cleaner environments, optimize energy consumption, and enhance water resource management. Through our analysis, we've discerned that SCD is intricately influenced by a myriad of factors, including Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), technology export, urbanization, and industrialization. Employing various econometric techniques, we've constructed a model to delve into the complex interplay between these variables, shedding light on their relationships and potential impacts. It's imperative for governments to adopt a forward-thinking, holistic approach towards understanding and harnessing the potential of SCD. Smart city initiatives must transcend mere technological advancements, instead embracing a multidimensional perspective that integrates various facets of urban life, including human and social resources. The primary aim of such initiatives should be to effectively address urban challenges, thereby fostering sustainability and elevating residents' quality of life.

To propel SCD initiatives forward, several strategic imperatives come to the fore. Firstly, cities should develop comprehensive Smart City Strategies and implementation plans, providing clear direction and fostering recognition across policy domains. Furthermore, these initiatives must be inclusive, seamlessly integrating diverse elements of city life and leveraging human and social capital alongside technological innovations. Prioritizing infrastructure development is also paramount, requiring a nuanced understanding of existing conditions and the establishment of achievable targets and priorities. Regulatory frameworks should be adapted to accommodate the complexities of smart cities, with policymakers considering broader implications beyond immediate benefits. Likewise, the enforcement of new rules and regulations tailored to support smart city programs is crucial for their successful implementation. It's essential to customize the application of smart city frameworks to the specific contexts of individual countries and cities, accounting for available resources and unique challenges. Embracing technological advancements, such as multi-modal sensors and expansive sensor networks, will be pivotal in driving the development of smart cities. By boldly embracing these strategies, governments and policymakers can pave the way for sustainable urban development and usher in a new era of enhanced quality of life for residents, reaffirming the transformative potential of Smart Cities Development on a global scale.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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